
The Role Of Political Dimensions Of Education In Ngugi's Weep Not, Child

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Abstract:

Weep Not, Child, describes an important stage in the Kenyan struggle for independence. It emphasizes the crisis between old and new culture. Ngotho, the centre of action in the novel moves forward the novel. The process of exploitation through education is introduced by Ngugi in Njoroge's character. The new education system put the young generation on the way of psychological slavery. The young generations wish to get relief from the oppressed situation with the help of education. It explores a betrayed community from the point of view of Ngotho's victimized family. His son Njoroge believes in education. In a later part he know the hollowness of the new education and culture introduced by non-native. After dismissing from school, Njoroge has joined the Indian shop as a salesman. His belief of raising the sun tomorrow remains a pure illusion. It has turned him in a coward. Ngugi used the weapon of education through the character of Njoroge, which is the counterpoising to the militant actions. Ngugi focus a light on the issue of education as related to the colonial agenda of diverting the people from the path of struggle. Ngugi asserts that colonial education leads many to detach and distance themselves from actual realities.

Keywords: Struggle, Education, Victimized.

The process of exploitation through education is introduced by Ngugi in Njoroge's character. The colonizers believe education as an effective way of producing slaves. The new education system put the young generation on the way of psychological slavery. The young generations wish to get relief from the oppressed situation with the help of education. They dream that they will be possible savior of Kenya. In this process they do not know how they were caught in the trap of the new educational system based on Bible and victimized. The teachings of Bible bring moderateness in Njoroge's nature about Whites. When Ngotho died and his brothers were in prison, Njoroge came to know the fragileness of education. Later he joined the Indian shop as a salesman. His belief of raising the sun of hope tomorrow

remains pure illusion. The new education system converts him in a coward.

Boro, Njoroge's elder brother has been sent to war. When he returns after war, he enters the nation of unemployment. Boro is frustrated. He represents the young generation of Kenya. The contemporary young generation is the product of colonial policies. Boro and Njoroge are two opposite pulls. Both have a common positive view of getting freedom from non-natives exploitation. "Ngugi's guilt at his own inability to participate in bitter struggle of independence from colonial rule in all probability manifests itself repeatedly at a subconscious level of his creative consciousness" (Cook, 3). When the Mau Mau activists started the struggle movement for freedom Ngugi was a school boy. So he was unable to participate in it. Ngugi himself

was the eye witness of the tortures faced by the Mau Mau activists. The activists struggle was for freedom from the colonial rule. Mau Mau is the outcome of repression of the Kenyan masses by the British colonial atrocities. So Ngugi glorifies the Mau Mau and its activists in his novels.

After dismissing from school, Njoroge has joined the Indian shop as a salesman. His belief of raising the sun tomorrow remains a pure illusion. It has turned him in a coward. He preferred a way of committing suicide: “Weep Not, Child is a novel which challenges the Kenyan youth to identify the salient features of their heritage” (Dhawan, 88). Colonialism has set up a system to finish native culture. The journey of Njoroge in the novel proves it. He believes in the new heritage. At last, he recognizes richness of his own heritage. Njoroge is the representative of young generation of contemporary Kenya. Mwhaki the schoolmate of Njoroge is more acquainted about the value of education. She remarks, “You are always talking about the country and the people. What is tomorrow? And what are the people and the country to you?” (Thiong’o, 1964, 106). The objective of the colonial masters of introducing the new education system is to create the native hands in order to help them in administration. In *Weep Not, Child*, Ngugi is concerned with the lives of individuals and their private dreams. But they are mingled with public concerns. His choice of Njoroge as a protagonist is right. Njoroge’s private dreams are involved with public concerns. For Njoroge education is the only hope of survival and it is the education which can avail them of their real status in their community. Ngotho and his family insist Njoroge to take education. Ngotho knows and experiences the adverse effects of illiteracy. So he decides to make his son a learned man. He says, “Njoroge did not want to be like his father working for a White man, or, worse, for an Indian” (Ibid., 44).

For Njoroge education means the medium of change and key to the future. Bible remained his favorite book during schooldays. He prefers a tales from the Old Testament. Njoroge is searching the way of freedom in education. His belief in a future for his family rests on education.

Ngugi in *Weep, Not child* explores the twin motives of education and politics. He describes the vital phase of Kenyan struggle for independence. Ngugi sheds a critical light on the issue of education as related to the colonial agenda of diverting the people from the path of struggle. Education, in so many ways, did play a crucial role in creating a collective amnesia as it made the exploited and oppressed masses willfully forget the necessity of struggle. It studies the ideological and political undercurrents of Kenyan society during 1950s which was the emergence of the armed phase of ant colonial resistance in Kenya. means. Ngugi used the weapon of education through the character of Njoroge, which is the counterpoising to the militant actions. He put much faith in education as weapon in his struggle where as Boro strongly believes in armed struggle. Njoroge's faith in Christianity and the goodness of man as preached by the missionaries as part of colonial education. Ngotho advised his son Njoroge to enroll in missionary school of Siriana. Education is everything, Ngotho, said Yet he doubted this because he knew deep inside his heart that land was everything. Education was good only because it would lead to the recovery of the lands.(Ibid.,43) This education exposes him to Christianity and gradually detaches him from his own religion and culture. The sway of this alien religion underlines deep implications as Njoroge grows up with a sense of acceptance and belief in Christian values of justice. Like many boys indoctrinated on Christian principles, the Bible soon became his favourite book and its stories the staple diet on which his young

fervent mind. Njoroje grows up placing his entire destiny in the hands of this Christian god who would ultimately offer the kingdom of Heaven as reward for good deeds. Like millions of other Africans, Njoroje also fails to see the real objective of the Christian missionaries and becomes trapped in ideological conflicts. Colonial education and religions are drawn in the course of civilizing mission. Growing dissent and resentment against the colonial oppressors indicate a move towards the inevitable struggle as the rising political consciousness transformed the social landscape. Exposed to Christianity with colonial educational background Njoroje believes that colonial education was the only potent weapon against the colonizers, thereby associating education with the struggle for freedom. Only education could make something out of this wreckage. He became more faithful to his colonial education. Kenyans use all their learning to fight against the colonizer. The contradictions between the idyllic world of Western education and the world of struggles with terrifying experiences affect the lives of all the people. (Killam, 1980, 49) The central issue of land and freedom seems deluded in the light of such obscurantist penchant for Western education.

Ngugi focus a light on the issue of education as related to the colonial agenda of diverting the people from the path of struggle. Education, in so many ways, did play a crucial role in creating a collective amnesia the exploited and oppressed masses willfully forget the necessity of struggle. Western education made you see the world the way the colonizers saw it. The colonial education exposes Njoroje to Christianity and gradually detaches him from his own religion and culture. But Njoroje did not want to be like his father working for a white man, or worst for an Indian. He does not want to be a slave to the western values that alienates him from his native roots. But the Bible is the source of inspiration for him

which brought out the change in his line of thought. He found some similar conditions in Kenya and the Bible. He compares the oppressed children of Kenyan with Israel. Njoroje compromised himself with the colonizer not to fight for the land. He became slave to the colonial education. He was deceived in the clutches of colonial enlighten process. His colonial education did not help him when his father was dead and his three brothers were behind the bars.

Gradually notions were strengthened for Kenyan freedom struggle. It became reality because of significance attached to colonial enlightenment by the Africans. Such beliefs eventually generated and widely accepted myth. Colonial education is the light of Kenya which brings salvation to the desolate millions was indeed a meticulously devised agenda. Njoroje's world is ultimately shattered by these tumultuous events and circumstances beyond his control. His final attempt to commit suicide also fails as he is stopped by Nyokabi and Njeri. Agony, pain and remorse fill him as everything before his vision collapse. Ngugi once again reinforces the bitter truth that education alone is not key to end colonialism in Africa. Ngugi's use of Gikuyu words and phrases in the novel is process of decolonization and aggression against the Western writings. Ngugi believes that literature politics are closely interrelated with each other because they deals with human beings. He strongly asserts that the primary aim if literature is not merely to entertain but also to persuade. Church and colonial education is the subservient to the interest of colonialism. Ngugi portrays not only the socio-political cultural situation in Kenya but also the national struggle for independence. Ngugi describes the contemporary Kenyan history which has myths and stories. Ngugi intentionally chooses the theme of education which is very controversial. There had been struggle for freedom and right to education in Kenya.

Ngugi asserts that colonial education leads many to detach and distance themselves from actual realities. Colonialism is responsible for immense changes in Kenya. Conflicts between the colonizer and the colonized are ruptured, destroyed and strained the traditional structures in society.

In short, Ngugi through the character of Njoroge presented disillusioned youth with disturbed mind due to colonial education. At last he realized that colonial education is the oppressed is myth. Njoroge hope that Western education might be instrumental to free from colonial rule. He strongly believed that the colonial education as the ultimate means to national independence. Ngugi penetrates deeply into the traumatic effects of colonialism. Ngugi used the weapon of education through the character of Njoroge, which is the counterpoising to the militant actions. Ngugi focus a light on the issue of education as related to the colonial agenda of diverting the people from the path of struggle. Ngugi asserts that colonial education leads many to detach and distance themselves from actual

realities. The imperative need of struggles to democratize society is stressed by Ngugi. He places the contemporary Kenyan struggle in a historical context and resurrects revolutionary heroes in the fiction so that masses are inspired. Ngugi made the history of Kenya during colonialism and post-Independence as the themes of his writings. He has become the most significant interpreter of his country's socio-political events, providing a picture of Kenya in transition.

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